

Detection of Cervical Cancer through Cytological Patterns in Papanicolaou Smears

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Abstract:

Background: A serious health concern is cervical cancer, especially in low- and middle-income nations where access to screening and HPV immunisation is restricted. Papanicolaou (Pap) smear screening is a vital tool for the early detection of cervical abnormalities, allowing for timely intervention and reduction in cancer-related mortality. Despite its effectiveness, inconsistencies in screening uptake and accessibility continue to pose significant challenges.

Aim: This study aimed to explore the cytological patterns of Pap smears and assess the prevalence of cervical abnormalities among women attending a tertiary care hospital in Patna, India.

Methods: A cross-sectional observational study was conducted. A total of 79 women aged 21 years and above were included based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria. Pap smears were collected, processed, and analyzed using the Bethesda system. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0, employing descriptive statistics and chi-square tests to assess associations between demographic variables and cytological findings.

Results: Of the 79 participants, 58.2% had normal cytological findings (NILM), while 41.8% exhibited varying degrees of cervical abnormalities, including ASC-US (12.7%), LSIL (10.1%), HSIL (8.9%), ASC-H (6.3%), and SCC (3.8%). The prevalence of high-grade lesions increased significantly with age, particularly in women over 40 years. A statistically significant association was found between age and the presence of cervical abnormalities ($p = 0.015$).

Conclusion: The study highlights a high prevalence of cervical abnormalities among women attending routine gynecological services, emphasizing the need for regular Pap smear screening, especially in older age groups. Early detection through screening can significantly reduce cervical cancer incidence and mortality.

Recommendations: Efforts should be made to increase awareness and accessibility of Pap smear screening, particularly in low-resource settings. Integration of HPV DNA testing with traditional cytology could enhance screening sensitivity. Public health initiatives should focus on targeted education and community-based screening programs to improve uptake.

Keywords: Cervical Cancer, Pap Smear, Cytological Patterns, Cervical Abnormalities, Screening.

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Introduction

The global health community is still seriously threatened by cervical cancer, particularly in low- and middle-income countries where it is one of the leading causes of cancer-related deaths for women. The primary cause of the illness and the reason behind 99.7% of occurrences of cervical cancer worldwide is persistent infection with high-risk strains of the human papillomavirus (HPV) [1]. The HPV vaccination has decreased the incidence of cervical cancer in many high-income nations; nevertheless, in settings with limited resources, the uptake of these preventative strategies is still below ideal [2]. (Pap) smears for routine cervical screening have proved essential in lowering the frequency of cervical cancer and its fatality because they enable quick detection of precancerous lesions

and timely care before the disease worsens [3]. Since its introduction in the middle of the 20th century, Pap smear screening has involved the cytological analysis of cervix-scratched cells in order to identify any aberrant alterations that might point to dysplasia or cancer. Even though Pap smear screening has been shown to be effective, access to it is still uneven, with notable differences seen between socioeconomic classes and geographical areas [4]. The high disease burden in India is partly attributed to the absence of routine screening programs for cervical cancer, which, amongst women, is the second foremost cancer [5]. Research has indicated that women frequently present at advanced stages because they have limited access to screening and are unaware of how

crucial early diagnosis is [6]. To overcome these inequities, recent research highlights the necessity of raising awareness about and improving accessibility to cervical screening programs. Community-based screening programs have been shown to greatly enhance the diagnosis of high-grade lesions and lower cervical cancer mortality rates, according to a study done in a rural area of India [7]. Furthermore, newer studies back up the combination of conventional cytology and HPV DNA testing to increase screening's sensitivity, especially when it comes to identifying high-risk lesions that cytology alone might miss [8]. In low-resource areas where regular Pap smear testing may not be feasible due to healthcare infrastructure, this practice is increasingly being promoted as a more effective approach. Understanding the present trends and incidence of cervical cytological abnormalities among women receiving routine gynaecological services is crucial, especially in light of the growing awareness of the significance of cervical cancer screening. This study aimed to explore the cytological patterns of Pap smears and assess the prevalence of cervical abnormalities among women attending a tertiary care hospital in Patna, India.

Methodology

Study Design: This study utilized a cross-sectional observational design.

Study Setting: The research was conducted at Paras HMRI Hospital, Patna, a tertiary care hospital equipped with advanced diagnostic facilities and a well-established pathology department. The study was conducted over a one-year period, from January 2020 to December 2020.

Participants: A total of 79 participants were included in this study. The participants were women who presented to the gynecology outpatient department (OPD) of Paras HMRI Hospital with various gynecological complaints and were referred for Pap smear testing.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

- Women aged 21 years and above who visited the gynecology OPD and consented to participate.
- Patients with gynecological symptoms such as abnormal vaginal discharge, post-coital bleeding, and pelvic pain.

- Patients who had not undergone a Pap smear within the past year.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Women who had undergone a hysterectomy.
- Patients who were pregnant at the time of the study.
- Women with a history of cervical cancer or those currently undergoing treatment for the disease.
- Participants who declined to provide consent.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were recruited consecutively as they presented to the gynecology OPD. Reporting bias was addressed by ensuring that cytological evaluations were conducted by experienced pathologists who were blinded to the participants' clinical histories.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a structured proforma, which included demographic information, clinical history, and cytological findings. Pap smears were collected by trained gynecologists using a standard technique, and the samples were processed and analyzed in the hospital's pathology department.

Procedure: Pap smears were collected from the ectocervix and endocervix using a cytobrush. The samples were immediately fixed in 95% ethanol and sent to the laboratory for processing. The smears were stained using the Papanicolaou technique and examined under a microscope by a qualified cytopathologist. The cytological patterns were classified according to the Bethesda system.

Statistical Analysis: Using SPSS version 23.0, data were entered and examined. A summary of the participants' clinical and demographic traits was provided using descriptive statistics. A chi-square test was used to evaluate the relationship between the cytological findings and the demographic data, and the prevalence of various cytological patterns was computed. For statistical significance, a p-value of less than 0.05 was used.

Results

The study had 79 women in total, whose ages ranged from 21 to 65 (mean age: 42.3 years). The age group of 31–40 years old accounted for 35.4% of the participants, followed by 41–50 years old (29.1%).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Demographic Characteristics	Frequency (n = 79)	Percentage (%)
Age Group (years)		
21-30	15	19.0
31-40	28	35.4
41-50	23	29.1
51-60	10	12.7

>60	3	3.8
Marital Status		
Married	65	82.3
Unmarried	14	17.7
Educational Level		
Illiterate	17	21.5
Primary Education	22	27.8
Secondary Education	25	31.6
Higher Education	15	19.0

Cytological Findings: Out of the 79 Pap smears analyzed, the following cytological patterns were observed (Table 2):

- **Negative for Intraepithelial Lesion or Malignancy (NILM):** 46 cases (58.2%)
- **Atypical Squamous Cells of Undetermined Significance (ASC-US):** 10 cases (12.7%)
- **Low-grade Squamous Intraepithelial Lesion (LSIL):** 8 cases (10.1%)
- **High-grade Squamous Intraepithelial Lesion (HSIL):** 7 cases (8.9%)
- **Atypical Squamous Cells – Cannot Exclude HSIL (ASC-H):** 5 cases (6.3%)
- **Squamous Cell Carcinoma (SCC):** 3 cases (3.8%)

Table 2: Cytological Findings of Pap Smears

Cytological Findings	Frequency (n = 79)	Percentage (%)
NILM	46	58.2
ASC-US	10	12.7
LSIL	8	10.1
HSIL	7	8.9
ASC-H	5	6.3
SCC	3	3.8

Correlation between Age and Cytological Findings: The cytological patterns were further analyzed based on age groups to assess any correlation between age and the predominance of cervical abnormalities. The results indicated that the prevalence of NILM was highest in the 31-40

age group (65.2%). LSIL and HSIL were more common in the 41-50 age group, with 21.7% and 17.4% prevalence, respectively. All cases of SCC were observed in women aged 50 years and above. The distribution of cytological findings by age group is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Distribution of Cytological Findings by Age Group

Age Group (years)	NILM	ASC-US	LSIL	HSIL	ASC-H	SCC
21-30	10	3	2	0	0	0
31-40	18	5	3	1	1	0
41-50	12	1	3	5	2	0
51-60	4	1	0	1	1	3
>60	2	0	0	0	1	0

Statistical Analysis: Chi-square tests were performed to assess the correlation between age and cytological findings. The results showed a statistically significant correlation between age and the presence of cervical abnormalities ($p = 0.015$). Specifically, older age groups (41 years and above) were more likely to have higher-grade lesions, including HSIL and SCC, compared to younger age groups.

Discussion

The study found that the majority of participants (58.2%) had normal cytological findings (NILM). However, a significant proportion of women (41.8%) exhibited various grades of cervical

abnormalities, with 12.7% showing ASC-US, 10.1% LSIL, 8.9% HSIL, 6.3% ASC-H, and 3.8% SCC. The predominance of high-grade lesions and carcinoma increased with age, particularly in women over 40 years of age.

The correlation between age and cytological findings indicated a clear trend: the prevalence of severe cervical abnormalities, including HSIL and SCC, increased with age. Women in the 41-50 age groups were more likely to present with high-grade lesions, while all cases of SCC were observed in participants aged 50 years and above. The statistical analysis confirmed a significant correlation between age and the presence of cervical abnormalities ($p = 0.015$), emphasizing that older women are

at a higher risk for severe cervical pathology. This finding aligns with existing literature, which suggests that the risk of cervical cancer increases with age, particularly among women who may have delayed or infrequent screening.

The significance of (Pap) smears in cervical cancer screening has been emphasised by recent research. 1800 Pap smears were examined in a tertiary care hospital study, and it was discovered that 79 cases had epithelial abnormalities. The most common type of lesion was (LSIL), which occurred in 32 cases (1.77%), followed by (HSIL), which occurred in 27 cases (1.50%). In order to lower the morbidity and death rate from cervical cancer, this study demonstrated the effectiveness of routine cervical cytology screening as a straightforward, non-invasive, and affordable tool for the early diagnosis and treatment of premalignant, malignant, and inflammatory disorders [9]. Liquid-based cytology (LBC) and traditional Pap smears were compared in a study conducted in Bengaluru. According to the study, the Pap smear had sensitivity and specificity values of 55% and 100%, respectively, whereas the LBC had higher values of 75% and 100%. It is possible that the LBC approach is more effective at detecting cervical lesions because it identified cytological abnormalities in 21% of patients, as opposed to 11% in Pap smears [10]. An additional study conducted in Nepal investigated the relationship between the histopathological findings and Pap smear results. There was a 55.55% concordance rate between cytology and histopathology in the 54 samples with intraepithelial lesions and suspected malignancies that were included in the study. Although differences were found in 44.44% of instances, this study highlighted the accuracy of traditional Pap smears in identifying precancerous and cancerous lesions [11].

Conclusion

The results of this investigation highlight the significance of routine Pap smear screening, especially for women over 40, since the incidence of high-grade cervical lesions and cancer rises with age. The findings emphasise the necessity of prompt intervention and early detection in order to lower the incidence of cervical cancer.

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